

Interoperability Policy Roadmap for the INFRA-ART Spectral Library

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Service: INFRA-ART Spectral Library

Service URL: <https://infraart.inoe.ro/>

Organization: National Institute for Research and Development in Optoelectronics – INOE 2000, Romania

1. Introduction and Context

The [INFRA-ART Spectral Library](#) is an open-access spectral database designed as a digital support tool for heritage research specialists working with spectroscopic techniques. Managed by the National Institute for Research and Development in Optoelectronics – INOE 2000, the database hosts a diverse collection of reference spectral data that can be reused across various research disciplines.

Scope of the service: The INFRA-ART Spectral Library serves as a comprehensive, dynamic database tailored for specialists working with (portable) non- or minimally invasive spectroscopic techniques such as X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, or Raman spectroscopy, among others. With over 2,000 curated spectra, the database allows users to analyze and compare the spectral signatures of a wide range of reference materials, facilitating the identification of unknown samples. The INFRA-ART database aims to be a trusted resource for researchers, fostering confidence in the quality and integrity of the data provided. The database is carefully assembled, curated, and maintained by application experts to ensure the highest standards of data quality.

Interoperability aspects: According to the European Interoperability Framework (EIF), interoperability is the “ability of organizations to interact towards mutually beneficial goals, involving the sharing of information and knowledge between these organizations, through the business processes they support, by means of the exchange of data between their ICT systems”¹. The [EOSC Interoperability Framework](#) (EOSC IF) is inspired by earlier work done for the EIF, and is structured according to the four interoperability layers² - technical, semantic, organizational and legal.

Technical interoperability refers to the ability of an IT system—whose interfaces are fully understood—to seamlessly interact with other systems, either now or in the future, for both implementation and access, with no limitations or under defined access controls. It encompasses elements such as interface specifications, interconnection mechanisms, data integration and exchange services, data presentation standards, and secure communication protocols.

Semantic interoperability ensures that both the format and meaning of data are accurately preserved and correctly interpreted during exchanges between systems or parties—in other words, “what is sent is what is understood”.

¹ EIF European interoperability framework - Introduction. Available at <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/nifo-national-interoperability-framework-observatory/1-introduction> (last accessed: 2 Apr 2025)

² IOPEU Monitoring glossary - <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/iopeu-monitoring/glossary> (last accessed: 23 Apr 2025)

Data interoperability, as defined by the OECD, is “the ability to combine and use data from different digital tools with ease, coherence, and efficiency”³. It facilitates the storage, processing, sharing, and recombination of data across various formats and locations, fostering seamless integration and enhancing the potential for reuse.

Interoperability of the service: At present, the INFRA-ART Spectral Library lacks adequate technical and semantic interoperability, which significantly limits both its accessibility and reuse potential. This interoperability policy outlines our strategic approach to addressing these challenges. It identifies current strengths and gaps, and defines strategic actions to enhance interoperability in alignment with the FAIR principles and the EOSC IF. This policy has been developed in the context of our participation in the FAIR-IMPACT support action [Creating EOSC-Compliant Interoperability Policies Based on the EOSC Interoperability Framework](#), carried out between February and April 2025.

This document serves as a practical guide for the data managers, developers, and data curators maintaining the INFRA-ART Spectral Library. It is a living document and will be reviewed periodically to reflect progress, align with community developments, and respond to evolving interoperability requirements.

2. Interoperability Problems

Using a set of questionnaires and checklist templates derived from the FAIRCORE4EOSC [Compliance Assessment Toolkit \(CAT\)](#), we evaluated our service’s alignment with technical and semantic interoperability practices. This structured self-assessment process revealed several critical gaps that affect the INFRA-ART Spectral Library’s compliance with the EOSC IF:

- Absence of API endpoints for automated and programmatic data access.
- Lack of persistent identifiers (PIDs) at the dataset (digital object) level.
- Missing machine-readable metadata schemas for datasets.
- Limited semantic artefact documentation (e.g., no mappings, diagrams, or example usages).
- No mechanisms for harvesting of semantic resources by external catalogues or services such as OpenAIRE.

The identified gaps not only hinder the service’s overall interoperability and machine-actionability but also present significant barriers to integration with federated infrastructures. In light of these findings, two key interoperability challenges have been prioritized for the INFRA-ART Spectral Library:

1. Development of FAIR Mappings and Metadata Alignment: Although the service uses structured metadata and applies open licensing (CC0), it currently lacks semantic mappings to external vocabularies or community standards such as DCAT, Schema.org, or DataCite metadata schema⁴. This absence of FAIR mappings restricts metadata interoperability and limits the ability of external services and platforms to interpret, aggregate, or repurpose the data. Without mappings, metadata is not machine-actionable across domains, reducing the visibility and reusability of datasets. Addressing this requires both the identification of relevant community standards (including semantic resources - ontologies/thesauri/terminologies/vocabularies) and the creation of FAIR mappings (crosswalks) between internal metadata elements and recognized schemas.

³ OECD Digital Education Outlook 2023. Available at: https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/education/oecd-digital-education-outlook-2023_12f8ebe3-en (last accessed: 10 Apr 2025)

⁴ So far, we have implemented DCAT metadata schema on the landing page of our data service to expose machine-readable common descriptive attributes of research data repositories (based on [RDA recommendations](#)).

2. Integration with OpenAIRE: Currently, the INFRA-ART Spectral Library is not integrated into harvesting or discovery infrastructures such as OpenAIRE, which restricts its discoverability in the European research ecosystem. Integration with OpenAIRE will require the implementation of automated metadata exchange mechanisms and machine-readable dataset descriptions, in alignment with [OpenAIRE Guidelines](#). Achieving this integration is a strategic priority to increase the reach and [reuse of INFRA-ART datasets](#) by a broader research audience.

3. FAIR Implementation

This section provides a more detailed analysis of the areas where the INFRA-ART Spectral Library falls short of full alignment with the FAIR principles and the EOSC IF, based on findings from the FAIRCORE4EOSC CAT self-assessment. The evaluation covered both technical and semantic interoperability, identifying several aspects where current practices are either incomplete or not yet developed. The table below summarizes the results of our compliance assessment across both technical and semantic interoperability dimensions, identifying current status and remaining gaps.

Gaps identified according to interoperability compliance assessment

EOSC Objective	Label	Criterion	Current status	Gap identified
TIF1	TIF11	Service MUST have a documentation associated	Available	-
TIF1	TIF12	Documentation MUST be open	Available. https://infraart.inoe.ro/about	-
TIF1	TIF13	Service MUST have an open protocol open to interact with	Open protocol but no API is being used at this moment.	No API implemented; limits automated access and programmatic integration.
TIF2	TIF21	Service MUST have an open authentication protocol	No authentication is needed. The service is open access.	-
TIF3	TIF31	Service SHOULD have a Service Level Agreement associated	No formal SLA (only Terms of use)	Lack of a formal SLA may create ambiguity in user expectations and service reliability.
TIF4	TIF41	Service MUST have an accessible documentation explaining how to access the data.	Available (on the website- Data access policy + related publications)	-
TIF4	TIF42	The documentation SHOULD be exhaustive. All formats MUST be described	Not exhaustive	Documentation lacks detailed descriptions of all data formats.
TIF 4	TIF42	The documentation SHOULD be exhaustive. The documentation SHOULD cover all access methods available to end users, both manually and automatically.	Not exhaustive	Missing coverage of automated access methods and full details on all access procedures.
TIF 4	TIF43	All formats MUST be described.	No	Missing descriptions for all supported data formats.
TIF5	TIF51	Digital objects provided by your service MUST have a PID	No PIDs for datasets/digital objects (only internal identifiers)	Lack of PIDs for datasets prevents proper citation, tracking, and integration

				with other systems.
SIF1	SIF11	Service SHOULD provide metadata about the service. Service SHOULD provide machine readable metadata about its features and capabilities	We use several data descriptors (metadata) to provide context, enhance data discovery, and facilitate data reuse. We have machine-readable metadata at organizational level only (to expose repository descriptors aligned with DRAWG).	Lack of full machine-readable metadata for datasets and limited interoperability with external systems. Need of internal mappings.
SIF1	SIF12	Metadata provided by your service MUST be based on an open schema	We use DCAT metadata schema.	-
SIF2	SIF21	Your semantic artefact MUST be licensed	Yes	-
SIF2	SIF22	Your semantic artefact SHOULD have an open licence	The metadata associated with datasets deposited inside the service is licensed CC0.	-
SIF2	SIF23	The use of open licences MUST be encouraged in guidance	Yes	-
SIF3	SIF31	Your semantic artefact MUST be documented	Not available	No documentation for semantic artefacts, reducing their potential for reuse.
SIF3	SIF32	This documentation SHOULD be open	Not available	Lack of open documentation for semantic artefacts hinders discoverability and integration with other services.
SIF3	SIF33	Your semantic artefact SHOULD reuse existing semantic artefacts.	Not available	Need of internal mappings.
SIF3	SIF34	Your semantic artefact SHOULD provide a usage example	Not available	No usage examples for semantic artefacts, making it difficult for users to understand how to use them.
SIF4	SIF41	Your semantic artefact MUST be published in a repository	Not in place	Semantic artefacts are not published in a formal repository, limiting their discoverability and interoperability.
SIF4	SIF42	The semantic artefact repository SHOULD have a clear governance policy.	Not in place	Lack of a governance policy for semantic artefacts, affecting their long-term sustainability.
SIF4	SIF43	Your semantic artefact MUST have a PID	Not in place	Missing PIDs for semantic artefacts, reducing their long-term traceability and citation.

* TI - technical interoperability, SI - semantic interoperability

Key compliance gaps relate to technical components—such as automated access and persistent identifiers—as well as semantic challenges, including limited metadata standardization and the absence of documented semantic artefacts. These gaps currently prevent the service from being machine-actionable, reduce discoverability, and restrain full compliance with FAIR and EOSC recommendations.

The following outlines the current status of our service and highlights the key actions we plan to adopt to address these gaps:

Technical interoperability gaps

While the INFRA-ART Spectral Library is publicly accessible and its core purpose is aligned with FAIR principles, its current implementation lacks critical technical elements:

- No APIs for data access: Data access is managed manually through email after a file access request; this significantly limits scalability and automation.
- No PID strategy at the dataset level: Individual datasets are referenced using internal alphanumeric codes, which are not persistent.
- No formal SLA or user support policy: Although access terms are defined, the lack of a formal SLA or structured support framework may limit transparency and trust for external users.

→ **Planned technical interoperability enhancements:** To close the identified technical gaps, the following standards and protocols will be adopted:

- ✓ Implementation of RESTful APIs using standard HTTP methods to enable machine-actionable access.
- ✓ Introduction of Persistent Identifier (PID) schemes (e.g., DOI, Handle) for dataset-level referencing.
- ✓ Revision and expansion of documentation, ensuring it aligns with EOSC's open specifications, security guidelines, and includes complete data format and access method details.

Semantic interoperability gaps

The assessment also identified several semantic interoperability shortcomings:

- Metadata schemas are publicly available but not expressed in machine-readable formats (e.g., JSON schema).
- Semantic artefacts (e.g., vocabularies) are undocumented, unpublished, and do not include mappings to existing community standards.
- There is no reuse of existing artefacts, and no governance model in place for semantic artefact lifecycle management.
- Metadata mappings (FAIR crosswalks) to established schemas (e.g., DCAT, DataCite, Schema.org) are missing, which reduces compatibility with external infrastructures.

→ **Planned semantic interoperability enhancements:** To strengthen semantic interoperability, the following steps are planned:

- ✓ Development of machine-readable metadata schemas (e.g., using DCAT schema).
- ✓ Alignment with domain-relevant ontologies and vocabularies; standardized terminologies used to describe spectra (data), materials, measurement techniques, and conditions (e.g., Chemical Methods Ontology - CHMO).
- ✓ Documentation and publication of semantic artefacts in public registries (e.g., FAIRsharing).
- ✓ Creation of metadata mappings (crosswalks) to recognized schemas (e.g., DCAT, Schema.org, DataCite) to enhance compatibility and enable semantic reuse.

4. Roadmap

To address the technical and semantic interoperability gaps identified in the previous section, a phased implementation roadmap has been developed. The actions outlined below are intended to guide the data technical team responsible for the development and maintenance of the INFRA-ART Spectral Library, ensuring alignment with the FAIR principles and the EOSC IF.

Interoperability roadmap

Stage	Stage description	Estimated timeline	Key actions to be carried out	Persons responsible for implementation
Stage 1	Interoperability Policy Development	Short-term (1-3 months)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finalize and adopt the Interoperability Roadmap as an internal guiding document. Engage with EOSC and domain-specific initiatives to ensure interoperability remains aligned with evolving best practices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INFRA-ART project coordinator
Stage 2	Technical Enhancements	Mid to long-term (6-24 months)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design and implement a REST API to enable machine-to-machine data access and integration with external infrastructures (e.g., OpenAIRE). Establish a PID strategy for datasets using a recognized service (e.g., DataCite, Handle). Begin exposing datasets with persistent identifiers and ensure all metadata is discoverable via the API. Review and update the current technical documentation to include detailed descriptions of all supported data formats and access workflows. Create and publish mappings (FAIR crosswalks) between internal metadata fields and established community standards. Express metadata schemas in machine-readable formats (e.g., JSON, DCAT, XML schema). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INFRA-ART project coordinator IT team Data curators
Stage 3	Semantic Artefact Development	Mid to long-term (6-24 months)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Document existing semantic artefacts (controlled vocabularies, internal terms, and data models). Submit semantic artefacts to trusted repositories such as FAIRsharing. Develop example use cases, relationship diagrams, and usage guidance to support community reuse. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INFRA-ART project coordinator IT team Data curators

Stage 4	Integration with External Infrastructures	Mid to long-term (6-24 months)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up harvesting mechanisms (e.g., via an API endpoint) to enable the federation of metadata records into metadata aggregators and search engines. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INFRA-ART project coordinator • IT team
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Align metadata outputs with the OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives to support future integration. • Consider integration with the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) 	

Guidelines and supporting materials

Throughout the implementation of the interoperability roadmap, the team will follow a range of guidelines, recommendations, metadata schemas, and ontologies, including:

- The EOSC Interoperability Framework⁵;
- Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) metadata schema⁶;
- The OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives⁷;
- The EOSC Pilot - EDMI metadata set⁸;
- The Chemical Methods Ontology (CHMO)⁹ for domain-specific semantic alignment;
- Research Data Alliance (RDA) recommendations and outputs related to repositories and dataset discoverability, such as:
 - Ten principles for improving data discoverability¹⁰;
 - Guidance on data granularity¹¹;
 - Guidelines for publishing structured metadata on the web¹²;
 - RDA metadata principles and their use¹³;
- The FAIR Principles and supporting guidelines from FAIR-IMPACT¹⁴, FAIRCORE4EOSC¹⁵ and other EOSC-aligned projects;

Estimated challenges during implementation

Challenges encountered in applying the above-mentioned guidelines include the lack of domain-specific examples tailored to interdisciplinary research fields and spectroscopic databases in particular. Several recommendations were found to be overly generic or ambiguous, often requiring additional interpretation and contextualization. Additionally, the team identified a need for training and support in areas such as metadata mapping, semantic documentation, and API implementation.

⁵ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d787ea54-6a87-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1>

⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>

⁷ <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/data/index.html>

⁸ <https://eosc-edmi.github.io/properties>

⁹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/chmo>

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/13384262>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00126>

¹² <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00066>

¹³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/metadata-ig/outputs/>

¹⁴ <https://www.fair-impact.eu/>

¹⁵ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

Recommendations to improve guidelines

To enhance the usability and adoption of these guidelines, it is recommended that more practical examples and ready-to-use templates be developed, with particular focus on domain-specific services. Additionally, providing targeted training materials and workshops on key topics—such as API development, persistent identifier (PID) policies for dynamic datasets, metadata standardization, and integration with external infrastructures like OpenAIRE—would greatly support implementation efforts. To ensure relevance across stakeholder groups, guidelines should be tailored to different audiences, including researchers, data curators, and IT developers. Clear distinctions in guidance based on user roles would help improve understanding and facilitate more effective adoption.

5. Validation

To ensure the effective implementation and continuous improvement of this interoperability policy, compliance with the EOSC IF will be verified through a combination of internal reviews, automated assessment tools, and peer evaluations. This multi-layered validation approach will help maintain alignment with evolving best practices while supporting the long-term sustainability and discoverability of the INFRA-ART Spectral Library. Validation activities will focus on both technical and semantic interoperability, using established metrics and tools discussed during the FAIR-IMPACT workshops.

Technical validation

- PID implementation: Persistent Identifiers assigned to datasets will be validated by ensuring resolvability through trusted PID registries.
- Open access compliance: Automated access to datasets via the API will be tested.

Semantic validation

- Schema conformance: Metadata will be validated against machine-readable schemas (e.g., [JSON](#)) to ensure consistency and interoperability.
- Publication of semantic artefacts: Artefacts such as vocabularies, crosswalks, and data models will be verified for public availability in at least one external semantic repository (e.g., FAIRsharing).
- Integration with OpenAIRE will be validated using the [OpenAIRE Validator](#), available through the OpenAIRE PROVIDE Dashboard, to ensure compliance with metadata and interoperability requirements.

Ongoing monitoring and review

- Regular reassessments using the FAIRCORE4EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) will be conducted to track progress and identify areas for improvement.
- The [F-UJI FAIR Assessment Tool](#) will be used to evaluate overall FAIR compliance, with special attention to the interoperability dimension—currently in an early stage of implementation (rated 2 out of 6).